

D5.1 - Guidelines on planned actions to empower women in decision-making processes

WP5 - Empowering women in decision making process

Lead contributor

Gema Antequera, CTAG

Adrián Lomba, CTAG

Other contributors

All MINDtheGEPs partners have contributed to this deliverable

MINDtheGEPs
gender equality in research

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Information in this report that may influence other MINDtheGEPs tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
T5.1 Supporting women in their self-selection into leadership.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Self perception of own abilities and definitions of what constitutes a “good leader”.
T5.2 Breaking down stereotypes on the nature of leadership at the top.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Leadership needs masculine characteristics. •Conscious and unconscious gender bias in definitions of abilities and of what constitutes a “good leader”.
T5.3 Breaking down structural barriers to women’s participation in decision-making bodies.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Show evidence on women’ presence in key role and bodies. •Present strategies for balancing gender gaps in decision-making processes. •Introduction of equality targets in administrative and scientific boards and in recruitment/promotion panels.

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List of acronym, abbreviation

Acronym, Abbreviation	Definition
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
CIRSDe	Centro Interdisciplinare di Ricerche e Studi delle Donne e di Genere
CICYTEX	Centro de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas de Extremadura
CTAG	Centro Tecnológico de Automoción de Galicia
D	Deliverable
EFT	School of Electrical Engineering (University of Belgrade)
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
EU	Europe
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
HEI	Higher Education Institutions
IBEC	Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia
KA1	Key Area 1: Decision-making bodies: gendering leaders and institutions
KA2	Key Area 2: Balancing Recruitment and career progression
MTU	Munster Technological University
R&D	Research & Development
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SDU	University of Southern Denmark
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
T	Task
UG	University of Gdansk
UJ	University of Jagiellonian
UniTo	Università di Torino
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction: MINDtheGEPs project

MINDtheGEPs takes a multidisciplinary multidimensional approach to challenging gender imbalances across five different countries with still traditional gender regimes (Italy, Spain, Serbia, Ireland, Poland) and across various types of RPOs: 4 public universities (Turin, Tralee, Gdansk, Jagiellonian) and 1 public non-academic research institute (CNR); 1 academic (Belgrade) and 1 private technological institute centre (Galicia). The consortium, led by the University of Turin's CIRSDe, comprises also three non-implementing organisations bringing complementary expertise in monitoring and evaluation (Knowledge and Innovation), research communication (Uppsala University) and scientific publishing (Elsevier). In order to promote systemic institutional change and following the "no data-no policy" principle, the project will map the existing data and, building on the tools developed within an ongoing research project of the project coordinator, will produce new quali-quantitative evidence. On this basis, both structural and cultural actions can be effectively designed. At a cultural level, the project will organise a virtuous chain of training, starting from across-partners "train the trainers" workshops to within-partners laboratories addressed to young women, but endorsing the approach of "fixing the system not the women", also to men and senior researchers. At structural level, the project will introduce work-family measures addressed also to men, equality targets in decision-making boards and gender-sensitive research. The establishment of proper figures and bodies creates conditions for the endurance of GEPs beyond the project's life. A multidisciplinary team (also including key-persons in middle or top management), coupled with a multi-skilled Advisory Board (including relevant national authorities), and 4 professional associations both in STEM and SSH, will contribute to a successful change in RPOs and in society at large.

1.1 Introduction and objectives of the deliverable

Deliverable 5.1, titled *Guidelines on planned actions to empower women in decision-making processes*, aims to provide guidelines to help trainers in designing the EMPOW_LAB¹ to critically address the widespread "narrative" that women have lower self confidence, are less competitive and have stronger preferences for family responsibilities than men, with the consequence that they self-select through different choices in terms of research field, time allocation between teaching and research, research and publishing research strategies. These guidelines will also help trainers in EMPOW_LAB to address the widespread notion that associates masculine characteristics with leadership.

After a short description of the methodology deployed to produce them, this report makes a series of recommendations based on the output information collected through different sources and develops a compilation of initiatives from different organisations in the subject of decision making and leadership to give trainers more and more ideas on how to deal with possible issues concerning this area.

Regarding objectives, WP5 specifically considers what is the best guidance in regard to empowering women in decision-making processes in research organisations. It is intended to help partners embed these practices in their organisations, thus contributing to the implementation of KA1 and KA2 of the GEPs. The objectives of deliverable 5.1 are:

¹ EMPOW_LAB (Empowering Laboratory) will train junior researchers (especially women) by means of three modules: (i) supporting skills development; (ii) deconstructing unconscious gender biases; (iii) becoming a leader.

- To increase awareness of the gender composition of recruitment/promotion panels and scientific and administrative boards;
- To increase awareness of gendered notions associated with leadership;
- To increase the gender balance in key decision-making bodies, both in scientific and administrative boards;
- To support the careers of women researchers particularly regarding their capacity to attain senior positions.

2. Methodology

To facilitate the work of trainers and offer good recommendations in training on gender equality in decision-making bodies, it is necessary to have a large amount of information of good quality in different organisational and cultural environments.

The way we have collected this information has been through five different sources:

1. Indications taken from previous tasks carried out within the framework of the MINDTHEGEPs project itself such as indications arising from the state-of-the-art review in T2.1 “State of the art review” or the narratives given in T2.6 “Qualitative analysis: interviews with male and female researchers at different grades, across all dimensions” among others.
2. Inputs from other projects oriented towards gender equality (such as GE Academy, GEA-Gendering academia, R&I PEERS, CALIPER, FESTA, GENERA, etc.)
3. Experience and existing actions from consortium partners. The MINDtheGEPs consortium consists of 10 different partners, each of them with a different form of organisation and with different initiatives implemented that can serve as feedback within the consortium itself to obtain ideas of good practices.
4. Additional materials provided by desk research, not only related to EU Gender Equality projects but any organisation that has been able to add value in some way in aspects related to gender equality.
5. Lessons learned through MINDtheGEPs workshops and activities. For example, at the “Train the trainers”, a two days training workshop to build capacity for sustainable change in partner organisations. Between 7-8 June, around 50 people met in Vigo (Spain) to discuss basic concepts and tools to promote organisational change, and how situated knowledge can support the implementation of gender equality plans.

The combination of all these tools served as indications to follow in order to develop the core of this deliverable, *Guidelines on planned actions to empower women in decision-making processes for research organisations (academic and non-academic)*.

Due to the wide variety of organisations that can benefit from these guidelines (academic, non-academic, public, private...), in the "Recommendations" section there will not be a specific final sentence that constitutes a recommendation itself, but these sections will be composed of information relevant to trainers in different fields and examples of how different organisations deal with these situations. In this way, the recommendation lies in the approach that the trainer can give for each field of application and in each particular situation.

3. Recommendations

Recommendation 1	Recognize and counter the widespread notion associating masculine characteristics with leadership
Recommendation 2	Promote Comprehensive Gender Awareness Training
Recommendation 3	Revise and Diversify Selection Criteria
Recommendation 4	Promote Visibility of Successful Women
Recommendation 5	Holistic approach

3.1 Recommendation 1: Recognize and counter the widespread notion associating masculine characteristics with leadership.

The first recommendation deals with the widespread notion that associates masculine characteristics with leadership. The data gathered from T2.6 “Qualitative analysis: interviews with male and female researchers at different grades, across all dimensions”, shows that women feel penalised when it comes to reaching top management positions or entering decision-making bodies.

In fact, data proves that it is not only “a feeling”, Fig. 1 shows that among the consortium partners the majority of department directors in every institution (except MTU) were men. This confirms the theory of the female researchers interviewed: top positions and decision-making seem still a male monopoly so actions to address glass ceiling and the importance of diversity management and leadership should be promoted nearly in each organisation.

Figure 1. Percentage of women deans or directors of departments in 2020

Even one male interviewed expressed literally that *“leadership is always seen in male terms and this is one of the main obstacles that prevent the leadership of female researchers”*. But while talking about the desirable qualities associated with leadership, the respondents mention the ability to work in a group, openness to people, diligence, charisma, as well as organisational skills enabling the acquisition of financial resources. Characteristics that are theoretically gender neutral but in practice leadership positions are still dominated by men.

Some female interviewees mostly believed that gender disproportion in commissions and boards is a consequence of sexist stereotypes and prejudice: women are afraid that their voices would not be valued equally as men’s, so they do not even apply for the commission membership.

Another circumstance that emerged from the interviews as a factor that distances women from leadership positions is motherhood penalty, the most recognized dimension of women penalization in the top careers in all the institutions involved in the interviews (albeit to a lesser extent at ETF). In the narratives, the motherhood penalty is explained because of the persistent asymmetrical distribution of care and domestic work between women and men, and between mothers and fathers. It is significant to note that maternity leave (and to some extent parental leave) is not considered sufficient as a measure of equal opportunities to address this long-term disadvantage. In conclusion, leadership should not be influenced by the fact of being parents, or having caring responsibilities and if they were, it is currently hardly noticeable thanks to the flexibility of remote work and other conciliation tools.

To address this issue, we found some examples of actions that could be interesting to consider, one of these actions was the mentoring programme Aurora delivered in MTU, a MINDtheGEPs partner, in 2019. The mentoring programme Aurora² is a women’s leadership development programme actioned under Advance HE³. The mentoring programme is targeted at women in academic, support and research roles in the University – from Postdoctoral up to and including Administrative Officer roles and Lecturer grades - in order to enable leadership potential and provide an opportunity for growth and development.

Aurora participants are required to have a mentor to support and guide them throughout and after the end of the formal learning process. Usually these mentors will have been identified by the HEI’s Aurora Champion, the central HR or staff development department and may be part of an existing mentoring scheme. Mentors may be male or female and be well-established and knowledgeable members of the institution who will usually be more senior than the Aurora participant.

According to the Advance HE website, mentors will:

- Be considered successful in their careers
- Be knowledgeable and experienced in their organisation and understand its culture
- Have sufficient time available to work with the mentee
- Have the endorsement of their Aurora champion
- Have sufficient general higher education experience to be able to offer advice and support
- Be a good listener and be able to provide objective, constructive feedback

² <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/programmes-events/aurora/aurora-mentoring>

³ Advance HE is a member-led, sector-owned charity that works with institutions and higher education across the world to improve higher education for staff, students and society.

- Have a genuine interest in helping women to develop their careers and particularly support his/her mentee
- Have a supportive or ‘coaching style’ of communication
- Be positive in outlook – able to appreciate the mentee’s point of view and see solutions
- Be flexible and open-minded

Figure 2. Aurora programme

Within the framework of this mission to eliminate gender bias in leadership, it is worth highlighting the AKKA⁴ programme, launched in 2004 by Lund University as an attempt to raise gender knowledge and awareness and provide methods and tools for structural change in leadership positions in order to achieve sustainable gender equality. Within this programme, leadership was understood as something that can be learnt and developed, and that focuses on the individual’s competences, and not on personal characteristics.

The overall concept of the programme was “Leadership can be learned, no one is “born” as a leader”. From 2004 to 2014 through five programmes AKKA has increased the number of females in leading positions, including top positions (1 deputy vice chancellor, 4 deans, 2 vice/pro deans) contributing to an enhanced visibility of females as leaders. It also helped to make more females interested in taking on a leadership role, Increased gender awareness in academic leaders – both females and males, provided methods to manage resistance towards gender issues in academia and put women as possible leaders on the agenda.

In conclusion, guidelines derived from this recommendation lie in:

- Recognize and counter the widespread notion associating masculine characteristics with leadership.
- Use data and evidence to show the existing gender disparities in top management positions and decision-making bodies.

⁴AKKA Programme: <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/good-practices/sweden/akka-leadership-programme>

- Promote actions to address the glass ceiling and encourage diversity management and leadership in organizations.
- Highlight the importance of diversity in leadership and its positive impact on organizational performance.
- Challenge sexist stereotypes and prejudice that discourage women from applying for commission memberships.
- Emphasize that leadership qualities such as the ability to work in a group, openness, diligence, charisma, and organizational skills are gender-neutral.
- Address the motherhood penalty by recognizing and mitigating the impact of asymmetrical distribution of care and domestic work.
- Implement measures to ensure that caring responsibilities, including maternity leave, do not disadvantage women in leadership positions.
- Consider implementing mentorship programs, like the Aurora program, to support women in academic, support, and research roles.
- Ensure mentors are successful, knowledgeable, have time for mentees, and are committed to supporting women's career development.
- Learn from successful programs like the AKKA program at Lund University.
- Emphasize the idea that leadership can be learned and developed, focusing on individual competencies rather than inherent characteristics.
- Foster a supportive environment where women are encouraged to take on leadership roles.
- Provide tools and methods for structural change in leadership positions to achieve sustainable gender equality.
- Implement actions that enhance the visibility of female leaders, such as showcasing successful women in top positions.
- Increase awareness and interest among females in taking on leadership roles.
- Increase gender awareness among academic leaders, both females and males.
- Provide methods to manage resistance towards gender issues in academia and emphasize women as potential leaders.

3.2 Recommendation 2: Promote Comprehensive Gender Awareness Training

The second recommendation is based on not sticking only to training for women, avoiding the risk of focusing only on one gender and thus avoiding the risk to reproduce gender biases. All people in each organisation, regardless of their gender or professional category, must be trained and aware of the importance of gender equality in decision-making bodies and leadership. As a consequence, the changes will be easier to implement and better tolerated and understood.

Awareness is important when it comes to making everyone aware of the existing measures and the tools available to them in terms of equality. This is something that emerged in one of the surveys conducted within D2.2 in the University of Gdansk that indicated a visible lack of awareness and information about gender equality measures preventing and dealing with discrimination: (e.g. sexual harassment and mobbing) among both women and men in the sample.

In addition, it should be noted that most people agree that measures of this type should be implemented. For example, in the survey carried out at CTAG, 93% of the women and 91% of the men who responded were favourable or very favourable to the implementation of awareness raising measures. As seen in Figure 3, results were similar for UNITO, where awareness raising measures are the second most supported actions to implement (only behind measures combating sexual harassment) with around 93% of respondents favourable or very favourable to the implementation of these awareness raising measures. This means that the implementation of actions in this sense should not, in theory, lead to too much resistance.

Figure 3. UNITO: Favour for gender equality measures in universities: share of people who were favourable or very favourable, by gender and scientific area

Precisely, one of the partners of the consortium (University of Gdansk) has included measures in this sense in its latest Gender Equality Plan⁵. In the frame of their goal to ensure gender balance in the UG’s decision making process (Decision making bodies: gendering leaders and institutions), they established

⁵ “Gender Equality Plan for the University of Gdańsk Equality measures for the years 2022-2023”: <https://ug.edu.pl/news/sites/ug.edu.pl.news/files/attachments/node/files/GEP%20eng.pdf>

a measure (Fig. 3) that will design and implement obligatory online training for all UG staff to increase awareness of the significance of equal participation of representatives of different genders in university management: “Participation of women and men in university management”.

Figure 4. Fragment of the latest GEP of the University of Gdansk

**Goal 2. To ensure gender balance in the UG’s decision-making process
 (Decision making bodies: gendering leaders and institutions)**

Measure 2.1.	Devising and introducing obligatory online training for all UG staff to increase awareness of the significance of equal participation of representatives of different genders in university management: “Participation of women and men in university management”.
Target group	All newly employed and current UG staff in the posts of professor, associate professor, adjunct – research and research and didactic path, senior/chief specialist – administrative staff
Timeframe	Commencement of work: 2022, course implementation from the academic year 2023/24
Units responsible	Devising training content as part of MINDtheGEPs. To be posted on the UG website and into the system: IT Centre, Personnel Centre Contractor – possibility of employing an external entity
Indicator	Number of persons trained: ultimately – the above-mentioned UG employees, in the test phase – a group of 100 individuals, 50 individuals per gender

In another consortium partner, MTU, gender awareness training is offered to all HR staff, those in selection committees, in addition to those in leadership roles. Training is also provided to managers and supervisors on how best to promote a positive working environment and their responsibilities under the Dignity and Respect policy and how to deal with complaints.

But not only academic institutions can implement such measures, CTAG, a private technology centre, also offers gender awareness training and events to all staff: for example, through the organisation of courses for all new hires.

Overall, guidelines derived from this recommendation lie in:

- Implement training programs on gender equality and awareness for all individuals within an organization, irrespective of gender or professional category.
- Ensure awareness training covers measures, tools, and existing policies related to gender equality in decision-making bodies and leadership.
- Emphasize the importance of raising awareness to prevent discrimination, including sexual harassment and mobbing.
- Incorporate mandatory online training, as demonstrated by the University of Gdansk, aiming to increase awareness of equal gender participation in decision-making processes.
- Extend training beyond academic institutions; private organizations, like CTAG, can also benefit from gender awareness programs for all staff, including new hires.
- Note that the implementation of such measures is generally well-received, with high percentages of favorable responses observed in surveys conducted at CTAG and UNITO.

3.3 Recommendation 3: Revise and Diversify Selection Criteria

The third aspect to consider is related to selection criteria. Many of the interviews with workers collected in Deliverable 2.2 (*Report on gender imbalances at meso-level*) focus on the criteria that are taken into account to reach positions in high management positions and decision making bodies. Interviewees are aware of the weight on career advancement of care duties and more generally of private life. They know that women can easily “drop out” since the academic system requires a full-life availability, in particular when coming at top-positions. One of the interviewees admitted the workload is unsustainable and that the prevailing of the quantitative criteria is worsening a situation already aggravated by “cumbersome bureaucracy”.

The main criteria underlying career advancement at top levels tend to be considered as gender neutral, especially in the STEM sectors, in all institutions involved in this research. However, the most important career advancement criteria assume the “unconditional worker model” (passion trap, strong identification with the workplace), and especially some women interviewed are aware that these criteria create gender disadvantages. Moreover, interviews reported other personal characteristics to be an excellent researcher including communication skills, emotional intelligence, cooperative work styles, as well as creativity and organisational skills, less considered in formal promotion criteria. The criteria of international mobility is also perceived as excluding young female researchers.

One example of actions taken to address this issue was implemented in Mondragon Unibertsitatea (MU) – Faculty of Business Studies Spain (Basque country). It was concerned with criteria for participation in governing bodies: When new members were elected for governing bodies, the criterion in the event of a tie was seniority. Historically, males have more seniority and, as a result, an apparently neutral and sensible criterion generated indirect discrimination. In this context, in 2012 the Equality Team of the Faculty proposed that the criteria should be changed, so in case of tie, the criterion of parity of the Governing Body would be first. The Governing Board approved this change and it is now included in the regulations. The change was made both for the Governing Board and the Social Board, and it was reported to all the staff in the Faculty. They also implemented some actions to promote gender-neutral selection processes such as:

- Jobs and job advertisements should be designed with non-sexist criteria.
- The selection team also should ensure that throughout the process (recruitment, selection tests, and interviews) a minimum number of both females and males are included.
- All the data related to the candidates involved in the process should be set out in tables in order to collect comparable and objective information on all candidates.

In conclusion, guidelines derived from this recommendation lie in:

- Reevaluate and reconsider criteria for career advancement, especially in top management and decision-making bodies, to ensure they are not unintentionally biased against any gender.
- Recognize the gender-neutral perception of traditional career advancement criteria in STEM sectors while acknowledging the potential gender disadvantages associated with the “unconditional worker model.”
- Broaden criteria for evaluating researchers to include personal characteristics such as communication skills, emotional intelligence, cooperative work styles, creativity, and organizational skills, which are often undervalued in formal promotion criteria.

- Address biases related to international mobility, recognizing that certain criteria might exclude young female researchers.
- Learn from examples like Mondragon Unibertsitatea, which revised criteria for participation in governing bodies to avoid indirect discrimination. Consider implementing changes such as prioritizing gender parity in case of ties.
- Promote gender-neutral selection processes by designing jobs and advertisements with non-sexist criteria and ensuring a balanced representation of both genders in the selection team and candidate pool.
- Implement transparent practices by organizing candidate data in tables for objective and comparable assessments.

3.4 Recommendation 4: Promote Visibility of Successful Women

After showing the facts about the numerous issues related to gender equality and access to high management positions and decision-making bodies, some women may feel even more discouraged in their aspirations to attain such positions. This aspect is what this section intends to address, a way of encouraging women not to rule themselves out for positions of great responsibility and, in fact, want to aspire to them, it can be the exhibition of many examples of women who have achieved great success in their professional careers and offer more information about successful women experts in different fields of knowledge.

An example is the University of Barcelona, which proposed to increase the number of women among the experts invited to participate in the events organised.

Considering previous analysis and example, to facilitate the task of finding expert and successful women in different fields, a summary table is shown below with different associations of interest when it comes to finding expertise or good examples regarding gender equality.

TABLE 1. Gender equality focused associations

Association	Achievement/ Expertise	Contact
ATGENDER ⁶	ATGENDER, The European Association for Gender Research, Education and Documentation, is a broad association for academics, practitioners, activists and institutions in the field of Women's, Gender, Transgender, Sexuality, and Queer studies, feminist research, women's, sexual and LGBTQI rights, equality, and diversity.	https://atgender.eu/guidelines-for-partnerships-requests/
BPW Europe ⁷	BPW International was founded in 1930 in Geneva by Lena Madésin Philips. It has grown to an international network of 25.000 members in more than 107 countries. Aim: Equal opportunities and status for women in the economic, civil and political life.	https://www.bpw-europe.org/contact/
European Women Association (EWA) ⁸	The European Women's Association is a global platform that empowers female founders by establishing a strong and safe foundation for women-led projects and initiatives. Through the European Women Association Platform, women worldwide have an increased access to: Funding, Business Networks and Education	https://europeanwomenassociation.com/contact-us/
EWORA ⁹	European Women Rectors Association (EWORA) is a full-fledged International Non-Profit association established in Brussels under Belgian Law in December 2015 to promote the role of women in leadership positions in the academic sector and to advocate gender equality in higher education and	https://www.ewora.org/contact

⁶ <https://atgender.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.bpw-europe.org/>

⁸ <https://europeanwomenassociation.com/>

⁹ <https://www.ewora.org/>

	research at European and international scales.	
Women in Manufacturing (WiM) ¹⁰	WiM has grown to be the only national and global trade association dedicated to providing year-round support to women who have chosen a career in the manufacturing industry.	https://www.womeninmanufacturing.org/contact-us

¹⁰ <https://www.womeninmanufacturing.org/>

3.5 Recommendation 5: Holistic approach

One way to approach gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making bodies is not to stick to one or another of the sections mentioned before. Instead of this, when possible, it is worth encouraging a change by suggesting a gender equality holistic approach for the institution, a strategic plan that uses the largest number of tools available to achieve objectives.

This implies using as many tools as possible at the same time (meetings, analysis, awareness measures, search and recruitment) to achieve an objective. Obviously, it is the most aggressive approach and not all organisations are ready or willing to face changes of this magnitude. However, it could be one of the fastest ways to change and obtain objectives.

This is the strategy that Šiauliai University took in 2014 in order to increase the number of female members at the top decision-making level. Considering the striking under-representation of females in the council, the ŠU's Council election tactics and strategy plan were developed within the INTEGER¹¹ project in order to encourage a gender-balanced representation of the council.

Several activities were undertaken in order to empower female candidates to participate in the university's council elections. Activities included communication with the highest management staff at ŠU through formal meetings, consultation with the university lawyer about the possible ways of increasing the number of female representatives in the council's election, participation in the preparation of the election regulations, and a search for female candidates from ŠU representatives according to criteria such as loyalty to the university and commitment to implementing gender equality at the university.

The strategic plan included the following 12 steps:

1. Development of ŠU Council election's tactics and Strategy Plan via active local team networking.
2. Appointing the officials, setting activities and deadlines.
3. Informing the Rector and Chair of the Senate about the proactive action, with regard to the elections and the search for an enhanced representativeness of females.
4. Detailed analysis of the current regulations related to the Council election.
5. Consultations with University Lawyers about how to smooth female representation in the election process.
6. Search for female candidates within ŠU's internal and external representatives (stakeholders) and students.
7. Recruitment of female candidates: assistance with the preparation of standard representative documents (cover letter, application-questionnaire), moral and technical support, and lobbying (university community and city).
8. Official recognition of the suggestions from the Centre for Gender Studies and of the co-opted candidates.
9. Design individual election campaigns for each of the candidates: image building strategies, publicity and communication.

¹¹INTEGER: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/266638/reporting>

10. Comparative analysis of the data provided by the candidates: gender differences, motivation and competence.
11. Observation of the election process (inside and outside) and construction of a management pyramid.
12. Raising awareness through publications on university and city media.

Outcomes and lessons learnt:

As a result of this initiative, the number of female members of the council significantly increased from 0 % in 2011 to 36.3 % in 2014. The 2016 ŠU election campaign strategy, with a holistic approach to gender equality, has been recognised by the EU institutions and named among the 10 best in the EU.

Lessons learnt from the process:

- Be prepared for the unexpected. Be aware that you may be confronted with academic (pedagogical & research) routines that may put some obstacles in the process. In addition, decision-making on the senior management level can be less democratic. Be ready to cope with structural and leadership changes.
- Be helpful, not obstructive. All interventions should be consistent with the academic life cycle referring to local/national law.
- Learn about the STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) culture features. Staff working in STEM fields have their own culture with its own characteristics. STEM professionals and disciplines usually rely on numbers, data and direct outcomes. Thus, they might not be the social sciences savvy when it comes to gender issues, gender sensitivity and equality. Capacity building, competence building, or awareness-raising trainings' content should follow an outcome-based approach. Traditional training is not effective. Search for non-traditional training forms.
- Knowledge is key. Keep in mind that STEM academics and professionals, as well middle and top management may not be gender sensitive. Thus, efforts to raise their awareness and build competences need to be made. The more people are gender sensitive, the easier it will be to move towards structural change.

4. Compilation of initiatives

There are more possible recommendations and many more examples of useful initiatives related to gender equality in leadership and decision-making bodies. But we have compiled in the following tables some of the most interesting initiatives that we have found and that can help trainers when tackling some of the most frequent problems faced by women who want to access top management positions.

4.1 MINDtheGEPs partners

TABLE 2. MINDtheGEPs partners' initiatives

Type of Action	Organisation	Initiative ¹²
Cultural Change	EFT	Training on Gender and Research, including on negotiations skills needed for the introduction of gender equality measures in research institutions.
	University of Gdansk	Devising and introducing obligatory online training for all UG staff to increase awareness of the significance of equal participation of representatives of different genders in university management: "Participation of women and men in university management".
		Opening of the bookmark Women in Science on the UG website showing the profiles of women in managerial positions and in university authorities and women researchers' achievements.
		Devising and introducing training in leadership skills, training to eliminate gender bias among managerial and executive staff.
	UNITO	Scientific event guidelines to promote equal opportunities also in the context of training activities such as, by way of example, conferences, seminars, webinars, scientific events.
UJ	Empowerment activities for women and other underrepresented groups	
Structural Change	MTU	At the final selection step, in the appointment process for new presidents (or equivalent), in so far as possible, the final pool of candidates will comprise an equal number of women and men. Where gender balance was not achieved in applicant pools a feasible detailed explanation to the Governing Body is required.
		In the appointment process for a new vice- president posts in any function area, a requirement of appointment will be demonstrable experience of leadership in advancing gender equality.

¹² There are no links to the actions because most of them are still not implemented or are not publicly announced yet.

	CTAG	Establishment of targets for women in governing boards and committees and targets for women applying as managers or high-level staff.
	CNR	The CNR published its first gender budget in 2021.
	UNITO	Monitoring of the increase in gender symmetry in the evaluation: preparation of a data schema to be filled by the competition office and to be yearly analysed by the Gender Equality Manager

4.2 Sister projects

TABLE 3. Sister projects' initiatives

Type of Action	Project	Organisation	Initiative
Cultural Change	R&I PEERS	CIC nanoGUNE	Mentoring to Promote Women Leaders in Research. Organise training sessions on team management and problem solving considering the gender perspective. ¹³
	LeTSGEPs	University of Tirana	International Workshop online "Improvement of women's careers prospects and gender balance in decision-making bodies in Research Organisations". ¹⁴
	GE Academy & Gearing Roles	GE Academy & Gearing Roles	Webinar: "Bias and resistances: Exploring challenges to gender equality in leadership and decision-making" ¹⁵
Structural Change	Gender-SMART	CICYTEX	Establish partnerships with training organisations in order to attract women to occupy more male-dominated professional categories. ¹⁶
	SPEAR	SDU	In order to improve the leadership support at a level closer to the researchers, all the departments at the faculty have now

¹³ <http://ripeers.eu/tag/nanogune/>

¹⁴ <https://letsgeps.eu/2022/01/university-of-tirana-presents-the-letsgeps-international-workshop-online-improvement-of-womens-careers-prospects-and-gender-balance-in-decision-making-bodies-in-research-organisation/>

¹⁵ <https://ge-academy.eu/bias-and-resistances/>

¹⁶ http://cicytex.juntaex.es/documentos/paginas/File/Plan%20Igualdad%20CICYTEX/Ingles_Con_Portada_PLAN_DE_IGUALDAD_CICYTEX_WEB.pdf

			introduced formalised structures for sections and Heads of Section to assume these responsibilities. ¹⁷
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4.3 Other organisations

TABLE 4. Other organisations' initiatives

Type of action	Organisation	Initiative
Cultural Change	Helene Weber Kolleg	Break the stalemate by getting more women into political decision making, improving their political career opportunities and creating a supporting cooperation network. ¹⁸
	University of Barcelona	Give the University of Barcelona Teaching Staff the guidelines that indicate the causes that can justify the lack of balanced representation. This makes it possible to guarantee compliance with the law and avoid any suspicion of arbitrariness. If the Teaching Staff Commission requests it, they can count on the support of the Equality Unit. ¹⁹
Structural Change	Siauliai University	Strategic plan to enable more women to run for the elections for the university's council. ²⁰
	Ghent University	New election procedure to ensure a gender-balanced representation in the highest decision-making body of Ghent University. ²¹
	Lund University	The AKKA programme aimed at raising gender knowledge and awareness and providing methods and tools for structural change in leadership positions in order to achieve sustainable gender equality. ²²
	IBEC	Increasing the number of women in decision making bodies: Every year when someone drops off from the International Scientific Committee (ISC), IBEC will

¹⁷ https://gender-spear.eu/assets/content/SDU_GEP.pdf

¹⁸ <https://eige.europa.eu/lt/gender-mainstreaming/good-practices/germany/women-power-politics-helene-weber-kolleg?lang=it>

¹⁹ https://www.ub.edu/web/ub/ca/sites/genere/docs/pla_igualtat/pla_igualtat_en.pdf

²⁰ <https://eige.europa.eu/lt/gender-mainstreaming/good-practices/lithuania/council-election-strategy-siauliai-university-council-election>

²¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/lt/gender-mainstreaming/good-practices/belgium/new-election-procedure-board-ghent-university>

²² <https://eige.europa.eu/lt/gender-mainstreaming/good-practices/sweden/akka-leadership-programme>

		propose the names of different women. 2 Women scientists have joined the ISC recently. ²³
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²³ https://ibecbarcelona.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/IBEC-Equal-opportunities-and-diversity-managment-plan-17_19.pdf

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